

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Axmedova Sharofat Kuronbayevna**Raxmonqulova Marxabo Melibekovna**

EL teachers, School № 8, Urgench city, Khorezm region.

Annotation: The following article is concerning the role of classroom management while teaching and its importance in developing both teachers` proficiency and learners` knowledge during the lesson. This piece of writing also provides some useful and effective strategies to manage the classroom proactively.

Key words: classroom management, model ideal behaviour, offer praise, encourage initiative.

Currently the government is mostly focusing its whole attention on the education at schools, colleges, lyceums and other institutions. In teaching process crucial thing that is considered to be vital is classroom management. Classroom management is a term teachers use to describe the process of ensuring that classroom lessons run smoothly without disruptive behaviour from students compromising the delivery of instruction. The term also implies the prevention of disruptive behavior preemptively, as well as effectively responding to it after it happens. It is a difficult aspect of teaching for many teachers. Problems in this area cause some to leave teaching. In 1981, the US [National Educational Association](#) reported that 36% of teachers said they would probably not go into teaching if they had to decide again. A major reason was negative student attitudes and discipline.

Classroom management is crucial in classrooms because it supports the proper execution of curriculum development, developing best teaching practices, and putting them into action. Classroom management can be explained as the actions and directions that teachers use to create a successful learning environment; indeed, having a positive impact on students achieving given learning requirements and goals. In an effort to ensure all students receive the best education it would seem beneficial for educator programs to spend more time and effort in ensuring educators and instructors are well versed in classroom management. Also, research from Berliner and Brophy & Good shows that the time a teacher must take to correct misbehavior caused by poor classroom management skills results in a lower rate of academic engagement in the classroom. From the student's perspective, effective classroom management involves clear communication of behavioral and academic expectations as well as a cooperative learning environment. So, there are given some effective universal classroom management strategies below to control the class

during the lesson, to improve and enhance teaching and to develop students` activeness.

1. **Model ideal behavior** - make a habit of demonstrating behavior you want to see, as many studies show that modeling effectively teaches students how to act in different situations. A straightforward way to model certain behaviors is holding a mock conversation with an admin, other teacher or student helper in front of the class. Talking about a test or other relatable topic is sure to:

- Use polite language
- Maintain eye contact
- Keep phones in your pockets
- Let one another speak uninterrupted
- Raise concerns about one another`s statements in a respectful manner

2. **Let students help establish guidelines** - encourage all students to help you build classroom rules, as you`ll generate more buy-in than just telling them what they`re not allowed to do. Near the start of the year or semester, start a discussion by asking students what they believe should and shouldn`t fly. At what points are phones okay and not okay? What are acceptable noise levels during lessons? This may seem like you`re setting yourself up for failure, but — depending on the makeup of you class —

you may be shocked at the strictness of some proposed rules. Regardless, having a discussion should lead to mutually-understood and -respected expectations.

3. **Document rules** - don`t let your mutually-respected guidelines go forgotten. Similar to handing out a syllabus, print and distribute the list of rules that the class discussion generated. Then, go through the list with your students. Doing this emphasizes the fact that you respect their ideas and intend to adhere to them. And when a student breaks a rule, it`ll be easy for you to point to this document. If you`re feeling creative, you can include the rule list in a student handbook with important dates, events and curriculum information.

4. **Avoid punishing the class** - address isolated behavior issues instead of punishing an entire class, as the latter can hurt your relationships with students who are on-task and thereby jeopardize other classroom management efforts. Instead, call out specific students in a friendly manner. For example:

- “Do you have a question?”, not “Stop talking and disrupting other students”
- “Do you need help focusing?”, not “Pay attention and stop fooling around while I`m talking”

This basic approach will allow you to keep a friendly disposition, while immediately acknowledging poor behavior.

5. **Encourage initiative** - promote growth mindset, and inject variety into your lessons, by allowing students to work ahead and deliver short presentations to share take-away points. Almost inevitably, you`ll have some eager learners in your classroom.

You can simply ask them if they'd like to get ahead from time-to-time. For example, if you're reading a specific chapter in a textbook, propose that they read the following one too. When they deliver their subsequent presentations to preview the next chapter on your behalf, you may find that other students want a bit more work as well.

6. Offer praise - praise students for jobs well done, as doing so improves academic and behavioral performance, according to a recent research review and study. When it is sincere and references specific examples of effort or accomplishment, praise can:

- Inspire the class
- Improve a student's self-esteem
- Reinforce rules and values you want to see

Perhaps more importantly, it encourages students to repeat positive behavior. Let's say a student exemplifies advanced problem-solving skills when tackling a math word problem. Praising his or her use of specific tactics should go a long way in ensuring he or she continues to use these tactics. Not to mention, you'll motivate other students to do the same.

References:

1. Soheili, Alizadeh, Murphy, Bajestani, Ferguson. Teachers as Leaders: Classroom Management Techniques, 2015
2. Berliner, Brophy & Good. Classroom management, 1986-1988
3. H. Korpershoek, Harms, Boer, Mechteld. Effective classroom management strategies and classroom management programs for educational practice, 2014
4. Dr Barry S. Parsonson, Evidence-based Classroom Behaviour Management Strategies, 2012

